

The transformative agency of university researchers involved in of a living lab on digital inequalities in education

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Abstract

The LaVIE project aims to reduce social and digital inequalities in education through a living lab initiative. In the living lab, the participation of research team members was closely monitored through co-creation meetings and barometer questionnaires. Their participation was analysed using the concept of transformative agency. The team's active involvement in the living lab beyond observation or intervention demonstrates their multi-faceted role as participants and leaders. The analysis was carried out from the perspective of manifestations of transformative agency. Our results demonstrate manifestations of shared transformative agency.

Key words

Living lab, research, academia, transformative agency, participation

Context

A team of university researchers from UQAR University is conducting an action research project in collaboration with the *Centre de transfert technologique* (LLio). The objective of the *LaVIE* project is to support the creation of desirable, feasible, and viable solutions to promote the adaptation of educational and pedagogical practices to reduce social and digital inequalities [1].

Living labs usually welcome members of academia for their expertise [2, 3] and some even take place in universities [4]. Our initiative has the particularity of giving a significant place to researchers since the research team leads the project subsidised by the Quebec Ministry of Education.

The project has, but not only, research purposes. The researchers contribute to the project through their expertise: they are experts in the subject matter of the laboratory and familiar with action research. In order to analyse the participation of research team members in the living lab, the concept of agency is used [5].

Methods used

Every step of our joint venture was closely monitored. Artefacts of participation are left on virtual walls shared during co-creation meetings, to which research members contribute. Some participate in the discussions; others opt to observe. In addition, each researcher is asked to answer a barometer questionnaire and research meetings were held [6]. These artefacts were used to analyse the agency of the university research team involved in a co-creation group of a living laboratory on digital inequalities in education. The analysis was carried out from the perspective of manifestations of transformative agency: resisting, criticising, explaining, envisioning, engaging in actions and undertaking actions [7, 8].

Results

In transformative agency, we paid particular attention to the posture of the research team as they questioned and critiqued, then explicated and envisioned new modes of activity, and engaged in actions and took steps to improve a situation.

Our results demonstrate manifestations of shared transformative agency, as well as proxy agency, notably through the involvement of several stakeholders in the project. While facilitating elements were noted, notably the team's adherence to the action

research in which a living lab is embedded, it was sometimes more difficult to reconcile the scientific rigour desired by the research team with the needs of the group's participants. There was little resistance, while members of the research team were very involved in the action. Whereas in a more traditional living lab approach, researchers are usually content specialists (which was also the case), in LaVIE they were the people documenting the content: managing the dual posture, between intervention and observation, tinged certain manifestations of agency.

The reflection on the critical posture of researchers, approached here according to transformative agency, would benefit from being discussed with the community interested in living labs, notably because the latter welcomes academia in its activities.

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